

Effect of Weathering and Parent Materials on Clay Mineralisation—Part III

B. DATTA* AND M. ADHIKARI

Department of Agriculture & Department of Applied Chemistry, Calcutta University, Calcutta

(Manuscript received 28 July 1972; accepted 10 November 1972)

Clay minerals from soils of humid tropical zones of India are analysed by chemical and physical methods. The formation of clay from parent materials are genetically interpreted in relation to ionic environment of the weathering zone. Acid igneous rock is the principal parent material, though, there are some calcium and magnesium bearing metamorphics. The former is highly rich in muscovite and K-feldspars. Ca, Mg and K that are set free from the parent rocks, under the weathering intensity have been removed from the weathering zone and hydrogen ions has entered dominantly in the soil exchange complex. The influence of acid igneous parent material and acidic ionic environment are responsible for the formation of kaolinite in such soils. Mainly K-feldspars and possibly muscovite in fine sand, under this condition of acid weathering, appear to be associated with kaolinite in clay.

THOUGH the present position regarding the exact reaction-mechanism leading to the formation of clay mineral is still obscure, the role of ionic environment yielded by the weatherable rock-forming minerals in the weathering zone has been unequivocally emphasised and is considered as one of the approaches towards clay mineral genesis. According to Grim¹⁰, in ionic environment rich in alkaline earth cations set free by the basic igneous rock under condition of insufficient leaching, montmorillonite is the product, while in presence of alkali cations, particularly potassium, illite will be formed.

Drastic leaching condition tending to remove these bases away from weathering zone, favours the formation of kaolinite. As is the case of the basic igneous rocks, the same holds equally good for the acid igneous rocks containing alkali and alkaline earth cations under conditions of differential weathering.

The purpose of this paper is to relate the mineral species of clays isolated from two Indian red ferruginous soils on distinct rock types (with the mineralogical make up of their sand and silt separates) and to study, in the light of discussion presented above, the nature of ionic environment that led to the formation of secondary mineral in their clays under the prevailing humid tropical weathering condition. To this end, profile samples of soils are analysed for the mineralogical composition of their clays by X-ray, D.T.A. chemical and physico-chemical methods. The mineralogy of coarse silt is studied by X-ray and is supplemented by chemical analysis. The mineral contents of fine sand (50-100 μ), degree of alteration of weatherable minerals in them and a more precise assessment as to the parentage of the soils through provenance study, are worked out (Datta and Adhikari⁵). A measure of ionic environment in the soil forming zone is deduced from soil

reaction, and nature and content of exchangeable ion species.

Material and Method

The soils included in this study were the red ferruginous soils from Manchkund and Padwa (Koraput, Orissa) belonging to humid regions. Characteristic physical and chemical data of the profiles and other details about the climate were described earlier (Datta and Adhikari⁶). Fig. 1.

Fig. 1.

Geological Sketch Map around Manchkund and Padwa Dist. Koraput, Orissa. (After Map. G.S.I., 1961).
Pleistocene & Recent Khondalites
Cuddapah Charnockites
Granites Unclassified Crystallines
Dharwarian

Geology—The ancient country rock is mainly ferruginous-schists (Krishnan¹⁵) containing much haematite and limonite and bands of garnet-magnetite

*Agril. Eng. Dept., I, I, T., Kharagpur.

rocks. The country rocks are intervened in monotonous repetition by alternating bands of a host of well-developed Archaean rocks of Eastern Ghats.

The principal groups are garnetsillimanite-schists and gneisses (Khondalite series), Charnockite series, calc-gneisses and gneissosegranites (Fig. 1).

Sample preparation for X-ray and D.T.A.—Clay fractions ($< 2\mu$) obtained by the international method were converted into H-clay by treatment with N/20 HCl and subsequent washing and centrifuging.

Coarse silt ($20-50\mu$) separated from sand by wet-sieving through 300 mesh sieve and repeated decantation (Jackson¹⁴) were cleansed of free oxides by the method of Aguilera and Jackson¹.

The entire clay ($< 2\mu$ size) and coarse silt were subjected to X-ray using nickel filtered CuK_α radiation and Philip's large Debye-Scherrer powder camera (dia. 114.83 mm).

Differential thermal diagrams of organic matter free clay in the H-form were obtained with the help of a manually operated D.T.A. apparatus.

Surface area—Total and external surfaces of "oxides free clays" were determined following the procedure of Dyal and Hendricks⁸. Y-value of soil clays was calculated according to the formula given by Martin and Russel¹⁶.

Chemical analysis—A complete chemical analysis of the entire clay fraction was carried out by Na_2CO_3 fusion method (Robinson¹⁸).

Free oxides were extracted by the reduction-chelation method (Aguilera and Jackson, *loc. cit.*) and free iron from it determined volumetrically.

Coarse silt was fused with $\text{Na}_2\text{CO}_3\text{K}$ and was determined by flame photometer. Ca and Mg were estimated by versenate titration.

Cation exchange capacity was determined by Ammonium acetate method as given by Peech *et al.*¹⁷ Exchangeable Ca and Mg were determined by versenate, Na flame photometrically and K by cobaltinitrite method (Jackson¹²).

Results

Base-exchange behaviour of whole soil : The results are presented in Table 1. In Manchkund and Padwa soils (soils being of humid zone) favourable leaching condition prevails so that H constitutes a major fraction of the total exchangeable cations. Percentage adsorption of exchangeable calcium and magnesium are fairly low in comparison to those in arid tropical soils (Datta and Adhikari, *loc. cit.*). Potassium saturation is also low. The distribution of exchangeable Ca, Mg and K along the profile is essentially the same in both the soils (Tables 1 & 2).

C.E.C., internal surface and Y-value : The results are given in Table 2. The values of c.e.c. of Manchkund soil clays compare closely with those of illite (Grim¹⁰). These values in conjunction with internal surface areas further point to the same. Padwa soil clay as judged from its characteristic exchange capacity and internal surface is most likely to contain

illitic clay mineral. The low Y-values of 9 (Manchkund) and 5.8 (Padwa) are, however indicative of kaolinite occurring also as an important component together with illite (Tables 3 & 4).

Chemical analysis of soils clays are given in Table 3, where silica and silica alumina ratio clearly indicates the presence of 1 : 1 type clay mineral in both the soils. A good amount of K_2O in Manchkund clay points to the presence of illite as well, in it.

Minerals in soil clays, X-rays : Lattice spacings and their relative intensities are given in Table 5. The diffraction pattern for Manchkund clay shows strong reflection at 7.11\AA (001), 3.55\AA (002) and 2.57\AA and (060) reflection at 1.49\AA . All these indicate presence of kaolinite. The line intensity and sharpness further disclose that kaolinite present is of well crystallised form. Kaolinite is confirmed on heating to 600°C which marked by the elimination of the pattern. A diffuse spacing at 10\AA with other reflections at 4.38 , 3.55 (003) and 2.67\AA (004) indicate illite. In view of the diffuse nature of (001) reflection and its intensity, it may be inferred that the illite is degraded.

In Padwa clay, the mineral appears to be essentially kaolinitic which is inferred from the strong intensity first order basal reflection at 7.12\AA and [002] and [003] spacings at 3.57 and 2.40\AA , respectively. Besides kaolinite, there is a trace amount of illite, the existence and quantity of which is detected from its very weak (001) reflection. (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. Differential Thermographs of H-clays. A, B, C,—Manchkund; D, E,—Padwa.

D.T.A. Study : The d.t.a. curves (Fig. 2) of Manchkund (15–60 cm and 60–120 cm) and Padwa (30–120 cm) are almost flat upto about 500°C , showing little loss of water at low temperature but give sharp endothermic peak between 567 and 602°C corresponding to dehydroxylation reaction. The latter

TABLE 1. BASE EXCHANGE PROPERTIES OF WHOLE SOILS (OVEN DRY BASIS)

Sample	Depth in cm	Percent absorbed		Cations			Base saturation at pH 7.0 (%)	C.E.C. at pH 7.0	pH
		Ca	Mg	K	Na	H			
Manchkund	0-15	14.57	11.22	3.19	5.48	60.50	34.46	20.2	6.42
	15-60	16.56	12.78	3.28	6.08	61.30	38.70	14.8	5.96
	60-120	32.99	21.20	6.02	5.46	34.32	65.68	14.5	5.57
Padwa	0-15	16.62	20.19	2.07	7.75	53.37	46.63	11.7	5.99
	30-120	38.98	23.32	3.98	4.78	28.94	71.06	13.4	5.20

NH₄ — exchange capacity.

TABLE 2. ETHYLENE GLYCOL RETENTION, C.E.C. AND Y-VALUE OF SOIL CLAY

Sample	Depth in cm	Total surface		External surface		Internal surface		C.E.C. meq./100 g.	Y-value/surface layer
		g./g.	sq.m./g.	g./g.	sq.m./g.	g./g.	sq.m./g.		
Manchkund	0-15	0.0423	136.6	0.0163	52.6	0.0260	84.0	20.5	9.0
	15-60	0.0451	145.7	0.0266	86.0	0.0185	59.7	18.2	
	60-120	0.0478	154.2	0.0321	103.5	0.0157	50.7	21.7	
Padwa	0-15	0.0322	103.7	0.0273	88.1	0.0048	15.6	29.3	5.8
	30-120	0.0392	126.4	0.0173	55.9	0.0219	70.5	26.3	

TABLE 3. ELEMENTAL ANALYSIS OF SOIL CLAY (OVEN DRY BASIS)

Sample	Depth in cm	SiO ₂	Al ₂ O ₃	Total Fe ₂ O ₃	Constituents (%)				Ignition loss (%)	SiO ₂ /Al ₂ O ₃ molar ratio	Free oxides of iron as Fe ₂ O ₂ (%)
					TiO ₂	CaO	MgO	K ₂ O			
Manchkund	0-15	38.39	26.82	14.80	3.75	0.54	0.62	3.49	11.19	2.4	2.05
	15-60	36.35	32.15	11.93	0.49	0.23	0.44	4.50	13.00	1.9	6.26
	60-120	40.01	31.36	14.17	0.30	0.26	0.38	2.31	11.97	2.2	1.17
Padwa	0-15	36.66	32.72	13.73	0.54	0.37	0.71	2.11	12.35	1.9	3.97
	30-120	39.60	33.46	12.49	0.50	0.40	0.79	1.54	12.47	2.0	4.66

endothermic feature followed by an exothermic reaction at 980°C indicates that the major mineral is well crystallised kaolinite in these clays.

The 0-15 cm samples from both the soils show, unlike the other layers, a very weak low temperature endotherm. This character together with the broad and hump-like dehydroxylation endotherm not typically sharp and intense like that usually encountered with kaolinite, and absence of exothermic reaction may indicate the presence of illite as impurity in a predominantly kaolinitic clay. A similar type of curve behaviour with the D.T.A. curves of mixtures of illite and kaolinite was also noted by Grim⁹.

Minerals in coarse silt: X-ray data are given in Table 5. The study shows that quartz is the predominant mineral in 20-50μ fractions of both the soils. Accompanying minerals are feldspars (Brown³) and mica, with a greater abundance of the former in Manchkund silt. Potash content (cf, Table 4) of this size fraction in different layers also substantiates that a fair amount of K-bearing minerals is present.

Potash content and simultaneous absence of Ca indicate that feldspars present are only of K-bearing types and no Ca-plagioclase is present. Mica in these samples does not appear to be one of typical primary micas which normally give well defined basal

TABLE 4. PARTIAL CHEMICAL ANALYSIS OF COARSE SILT (OVEN DRY BASIS)

Sample	Depth in cm	C.E.C. meq/100 gm	Constituents (%)		
			K	Mg	Ca
Manchkund	0-15	2.2	1.6	0.56	—
	15-60	2.4	1.8	0.39	—
	60-120	2.2	2.3	0.33	—
Padwa	0-15	3.9	2.4	—	—
	30-120	3.5	2.2	—	—

reflections. Presence of mica here, is detected from a reflection at 10.987Å and 11.354Å in Manchkund and Padwa, respectively. No subsequent lower

TABLE 5. LATTICE SPACING IN Å AND THEIR RELATIVE INTENSITIES IN POWDER DIAGRAMS

Soil	H-clay				Coarse silt			
	Lattice spacing comparable with kaolinite		Lattice spacing comparable with illite		Lattice spacing comparable with feldspar group		Lattice spacing comparable with quartz	
	d_{hkl}	I	d_{hkl}	I	d_{hkl}	I	d_{hkl}	I
Manchkund (0-15 cm)	7.11	7	10.0	(diffuse)	6.4958	$\frac{1}{2}$	3.3285	10
	3.5503	3	4.3879	5	5.8087	$\frac{1}{3}$	2.7809	1
	2.5743	1	3.5503	4	4.2467	6	2.5916	2
	1.4955	$\frac{1}{2}$	2.6742	$\frac{1}{3}$	3.754	4	2.4609	1
			1.4955	$\frac{1}{2}$	3.474	1	2.2939	1
					3.2268	3	2.251	$\frac{1}{2}$
					2.9975	$1\frac{1}{2}$	2.1281	2
					2.9042	$1\frac{1}{2}$	1.9910	1
							1.9363	$\frac{1}{3}$
							1.8253	$4\frac{1}{2}$
							1.8064	$4\frac{1}{2}$
							1.6822	3
							1.5480	5
							1.5025	$\frac{1}{2}$
						1.4588	1	
						1.3789	7	
						1.2901	$1\frac{1}{2}$	
Padwa (0-15 cm)	7.1204	10		(very diffuse)			3.3285	10
	4.48	5	10.0	3	4.2029	7	2.4518	5
	4.1295	3	4.5997	1			2.2805	5
	3.5785	3	3.3507	6			2.2317	3
	2.40	5	1.4955				2.1252	5
	2.4926	4					1.9811	5
	2.2939	2					1.8151	6
	2.0112	2					1.6749	5
	1.4955	6					1.5438	6
							1.4572	$2\frac{1}{2}$
							1.3774	$6\frac{1}{2}$
							1.2925	3
							1.259	4
							1.2325	3
						1.2031	5	
						1.185	$5\frac{1}{2}$	
						1.157	$3\frac{1}{2}$	

I = Intensity of lines.

order basal spacings could be obtained. The (001) spacings as obtained, being larger than the usual values (9.9Å, 10Å) for mica, indicate that mica present is possibly hydrated or interstratified. Exchange capacity (cf. table) also accounts for the presence of a small amount of such secondary mineral in silt.

Discussions

These soils are developed *in situ* from the Archaean rocks of the Eastern Ghats¹⁵ under humid climatic condition. The underlying parent material is composed mainly of acid igneous and some mixed metamorphic rocks (Datta and Adhikari⁵). The latter are mainly mica-schist with a minor amount of tremolite-schist in Manchkund and calc-gneiss in case of Padwa. The dominating influence of the parent rocks is reflected in the accessory mineral suite of the fine sands where a conspicuous abundance of zircon in particular, points to the presence of acidic parent material. The latter are also highly rich in K-feldspars and muscovite, K-feldspars being in states of alteration. Compared to K-feldspars plagioclase occurs in very small amount. It is

chiefly basic (towards anorthite in Padwa) and fairly altered.

Adherence of a fair amount of K-feldspars and total extinction of plagioclase in silt size fraction indicates more weatherability of soda-lime feldspars compared to their potassium analogues. This may also suggest that silt fractions of these soils are chemically more reactive than their sand fractions.

Distinctly acid reaction and good content of free oxides of iron (Table 3) in association with clay particles indicate an intense weathering condition of leaching. Whatever Ca^{++} , Mg^{++} and K^+ are set by the basic and K-bearing components of the parent rock, might have been, under these circumstances, removed away from the weathering zone of the soils. As a result, influence of parent material containing basic component (cf. calc. schist) whatever little is there is masked and H-ions constitute a large proportion of the exchangeable bases.

The dominance of kaolinite in these clays appears to be associated with the weathering of feldspars, mainly K-feldspars, present in fair amount of both sand and silt fractions.

Under the prevailing acidic soil environment the hydrolytic decomposition of the feldspars might result in a pronounced leaching of bases, particularly K and Ca, leading finally to the production of kaolinite (Keller¹³). Similar conclusion was arrived at by De Kime *et al.*⁷, Keller *et al.*¹³ and Correns⁴.

When mica weathers, H⁺ gradually replaces K⁺ and the mineral is hydrated forming hydro-mica (Bates²) ultimately passing on to kaolin. Large abundance of muscovite in fine sands and appearance of hydro-mica phase (Datta and Adhikari, *loc. cit.*) in them, indicate mica weathering and its possible alteration to kaolin in these soils. This may be another reasonable mechanism of kaolin formation in these soils. It has also been observed by Sand¹⁹ that micas weather to kaolinite under fairly intensive weathering environment.

Whatever may be the mechanism, it may be inferred that acid granitic parent material and pronounced leaching weathering condition leading to an acid environment, have favoured the formation of kaolin in these soils.

Results go to show that though the mineral composition in both these soils is essentially kaolinitic, the proportion is relatively more in Padwa clay, while in Manchkund it is diluted by a little or more illite.

Formed on the same nature of parent material and identical climate being within a latitudinal and longitudinal variation range of 9' and 7' respectively (situated at a short distance), this minor but tangible variation is interesting to note. This anomaly can be explained if we take into account the greater intensity of leaching weathering condition in Padwa soil as evidenced from comparatively lower pH, and higher clay content and free oxides of iron associated with clay. Variation in these properties under similar set of climatic factors is presumed to

have been brought about by some microclimatic influence inside Padwa soil and possibly, the latter bringing forth an enhanced leaching effectiveness that has been responsible for a relatively more content of kaolin as compared to that in Manchkund soil clay.

References

1. N. H. AGUILERA and M. L. JACKSON, *Soil Sci. Amer. Proc.*, 1953, **17**, 359-364.
2. T. F. BATES, *Mineral Industries*, Pennsylvania State Univ., 1960, **29**(8), 1.
3. G. BROWN, in "The X-ray identification and crystal structures of clay minerals", pp. 467-488, Mineralog. Soc. (clay minerals group), London, 1961.
4. C. W. CORRENS, 10th Conf. of clays and clay minerals, pp. 443-459, Pergamon Press, New York, 1963.
5. B. DATTA and M. ADHIKARI, *Agrokemia es Talajitum (supplementum)*, 1968, **17**, 125-141.
6. B. DATTA and M. ADHIKARI, *Indian J. Appl. Chem.*, 1968, **31**, 143-150.
7. C. DE KIMPE, M. C. GASTUCHE and S. W. BRINDLEY, *Am. Min.*, 1961, **46**, 1370-1382.
8. R. S. DYAL and S. B. HENDRICKS, *Soil. Sci.*, 1950, **69**, 421-432.
9. R. E. GRIM, *Am. Min.*, 1947, **32**, 493-501.
10. R. E. GRIM, "Clay Mineralogy", McGraw-Hill, New York, 1953.
11. M. L. JACKSON, "Soil Chemical Analysis: Advance Course", Wisconsin Univ., Madison, 1956.
12. M. L. JACKSON, "Soil Chemical Analysis", Prentice Hall, New Jersey, 1958.
13. W. D. KELLER, "Soil Clay Mineralogy." (Eds. C. I. Rich and G. W. Kunze), Univ. North Carolina Press, 1964.
14. W. D. KELLER, W. D. BALGORD and A. L. REESMAN, *J. Sed. petrol.*, 1963, **33**, 191-204.
15. M. S. KRISHNAN, "Geology of India and Burma", Higginbotham, Madras, 1960.
16. R. T. MARTIN and M. B. RUSSEL, *Soil Sci.*, 1952, **74**, 267-269.
17. M. PEECH, USDA Circ. No. 757, 1947.
18. W. C. ROBINSON, "Method and Procedure of Soil Analysis used in the Division of Soil Chemistry and Physics", USDA Circ. 1939.
19. L. B. SAND, *Am. Min.*, 1956, **41**, 28-40.